

JUSTICE FOR EVERY CHILD: ANALYSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL COURTS UNDER POCSO

Flori Dwivedi

Research Scholar, Institute of Legal Studies, Shri Ram Swaroop Memorial University,
Lucknow- Deva Road, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, 225003

E-mail ID: floridwivedi16@gmail.com

Dr. Shruti Sharma

Associate Professor, Institute of Legal Studies, Shri Ram Swaroop Memorial University,
Lucknow- Deva Road, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, 225003

E-mail: shrutisharma.ils@srmu.ac.in

Article Info

Received : 10 Mar 2026
Revised: 28-Apr-2026
Accepted : 28 May 2026
Published online: 06-Jun-2026

Cite This Article As

Flori D & Shruti S (2026), "Justice For Every Child: Analysing the Role of Special Courts under POCSO", International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research, Volume 13, Issue 1, 2026, pp 60-65. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20570423>

©2026 By the Author. Published By ARSEAM Foundation. This article is an open access article published & distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. The full terms of this license may be seen at : <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

The Journal follows the Best Practice guidelines and this statement is based on the guidelines and standards developed by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE): <https://publicationethics.org/>

ABSTRACT

In order to provide timely justice to the child victims of sexual abuse in India, this article explores the function of Special Courts established by the POCSO Act. India, with the world's largest child population, faces alarming rates of crimes against children, including sexual abuse, kidnapping, and physical assault. In 2012, lawmakers sought to solve these problems by establishing Special Courts to handle cases involving children in a way that is both fair and expedited.

The main intention of the study is to test the effectiveness of Special Courts to protect the rights of child victims, identify the challenges at the implementation level and examine the consequences of delays in judicial procedures, inadequate infrastructure facilities, and victim support measures.

The study finds that despite various efforts and attempt in providing a child-centric legal environment, issues such as overwhelming list of pending cases, long durations of trials, and nonavailability of infrastructure exist for the Special Courts. Also, despite provisions made for timely trials through legislation, many cases remain undeterred and repeated appearances of children in court intensifies trauma. Besides this, victim compensation and rehabilitation practices are not uniform among all the states.

While special courts under the POCSO Act are an important step towards protecting children, much needs to be done through systemic reforms. Improvement in the court infrastructure, judicial training, victim support services, and case management are some of the critical elements to make these courts deliver what is intended-that is, just, prompt outcomes for child victims.

Keywords: POCSO, Child Safety, Sexual Abuse, Child Victims, Special Courts

INTRODUCTION

Crime is a universal phenomenon and truly speaking it is impossible to find a society free from crime and criminals. Like adult criminal behaviour, deviant behaviour among children

is witnessed if not taken proper care at young and tender age. Therefore, it important to handle young minds with patience, dedication and care. Talking about India approximately 444 million fall under the category of 'a child' as they are below the age of 18. It to be noted that India boasts the world's highest child population hence, it is common for parents to ignore their children when they have a big family. Multiple crimes target children without proper parental care. More than 350 crimes involving minors are recorded daily in India, according to the National Crime Records Bureau. Physical violence, which could kill or maim the child for life, is the bulk of these crimes. Sexual offences account for 38% of these crimes, while murder and kidnapping account for 40%¹.

Protecting the rights of victims who are minors is a fundamental function of the justice system. Such crimes might be punished by either a particular law or the Indian Penal Code of 1860. The horrifying acts of sexual abuse and exploitation of children were addressed by passing a particular law in 2012 known as the POSCO Act. Severe penalties for the horrible crimes of sexual abuse and exploitation of children were the driving forces behind the passage of this law. On June 19, 2012, this statute became law. For the purpose of handling cases involving crimes perpetrated against minors, this statute authorised the establishment of "Special Courts" in every court district. In toto 409 special courts in operation in 30 states and territories as of March 2024. There have been 2,29,361 cases decided by these courts thus far. These courts hear cases involving various types of sexual assault, including penetrative and aggravated penetrative assault²

The new law establishes Special Courts with extensive powers and procedures compared to other nations. The power to issue life sentences, the death penalty (subsequently added in 2018 amendment), and other severe punishments is granted to a "Special Court" by the law. Failure to disclose a sexual crime against a child is a serious infraction under the law. A minor can file a report of a crime that occurred years ago in India because the country has abolished the statute of limitations. Disclosures that could reveal the victim's identity are strictly prohibited by law. The benchmarks study known as the Out of the Shadows Index (OOSI) for 2022 put India's child protection laws fifth. Out of 60 nations surveyed, India ranked fifteenth for the strength of its legislation and policies against sexual abuse and violence against children³

The major goal of this research is to find out how well the specialised courts in India help children who have been victims of sexual abuse or exploitation get justice.

The Foundations of Special Courts

Section 28 (1) of the POCSO Act states that in order to speed up the court proceedings for offences under the Act, state legislatures must agree with the head of justice of the HC to create a Sessions Court as a Special Court. The Bill's Standing Committee's Report suggested leveraging the current legal structures of the Commissions for Preservation of Child Rights Act, 2005 rather than squandering resources on new courts or infrastructure-building projects.

It is important to recognise that children have particular needs, and this paragraph takes into account such requirements. Children are inherently fragile. A child who has been the victim

¹India recorded over 350 crimes against children each day in 2020: NCRB Data (2024) Outlook India.

Available at: <https://www.outlookindia.com/website/story/india-news-india-recorded-over-350-crimes-against-children-each-day-in-2020/396394> (Accessed: 16 December 2024).

²Fast track special courts (ftscs) | department of justice | india. Available at: <https://doj.gov.in/fast-track-special-court-ftscs/> (Accessed: 16 December 2024).

³Ferrao, R. (2024) 'Special Courts for Children; Lessons learnt from India', *International Journal for Court Administration*, 15(2). doi:10.36745/ijca.485.

of abuse may experience long-term psychological stress. In cases involving POCSO, it is absolutely necessary to have a profound comprehension of the complexities of abuse. Before everything else, it is essential to give priority to providing assistance to the child, organising testimony and evidence with compassion, and protecting the child's right to privacy. The goal of this provision is to facilitate a speedy trial by mandating that all matters pertaining to POCSO be tried exclusively in Special Courts that have been specifically formed for the purpose of addressing comparable issues. The objective of this piece of law is to guarantee that Special Public Prosecutors (SPPs) and judges have a comprehensive understanding of cases that involve sexual offences and victims who are under the age of 18.

Nevertheless, Special Courts are not required by the POCSO Act to exclusively deal with POCSO offences or crimes perpetrated against children. The lack of exclusivity causes hearings to be postponed, judges and SPPs to be overworked, and the child to be exposed to other accused individuals, police, and attorneys during trial. Screens, separate entrances, waiting rooms, and a generally child-friendly environment might help reduce the child's exposure to the accused, but these structural adjustments are difficult to accomplish. Children cannot have a specialised court system that handles all types of cases. Further complicating issues is the fact that judges and SPPs must constantly switch their attention between cases involving POCSO and other subjects⁴.

Direct Cognizance by the Specialized Court

Under the Act, Specialized Courts can take direct cognizance of crimes against minors without requiring committal proceedings by a Magistrate (Section 33(1), POCSO Act). This saves the time and allows police to directly bring cases to the Special Court, ensuring that trials of child sexual abuse cases take place promptly. Decisions of High Courts support the cognizance of Special Courts, though in some cases, the Magistrates still deliver the accused.

Child related cases are dealt by the Special Courts, so children-friendly proceedings and protecting child rights are the purposes that these courts serve. For the first time, juvenile court was established in 2004 in Goa as Goa Children's Court, while other Special Courts were initiated with the POCSO Act in 2016 across Delhi, Telangana, and Karnataka. State governments and the Chief Justice of the High Court work together to setup these courts, which are suitable for child in procedure but have the same authorities as Sessions Courts. The court provides separate spaces for children to play and testify, as well as safeguards to ensure that they do not come into direct contact with the accused⁵.

Special Courts prioritize swift justice, requiring in-camera child statements within 30 days, ensuring the presence of a parent or guardian, and limiting child testimony to one session to minimize trauma. Judges handle questioning, prohibiting aggressive behaviour from lawyers. The courts can issue arrest warrants, ensure the accused appear for trial, and provide fair trials while protecting minors from contact with the accused.

In cases of conviction, punishment includes imprisonment and fines to be paid to the victim who is compensated through District Legal Services Authority. These courts play an

⁴Raha. S. (2023) *Structural and procedural compliance by Special Courts under the POCSO Act by ms. Swagata Raha: Haq : Centre for child rights, HAQ*. Available at: <https://www.haqcrc.org/juvenile-justice/children-from-sexual-abuse-presentation/structural-procedural-compliance-special-courts-pocso-act-ms-swagata-raha/> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

⁵Sakshi (2017) *What is special about special courts?*, *The Hindu*. Available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/op-ed/What-is-special-about-special-courts/article16978952.ece> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

important role in ensuring a child-friendly environment, preserving the dignity of victims, reducing delay, and efficiently dealing with child sexual abuse cases⁶.

The Rights of Children under Specialized Courts

A special circumstance develops when a family member or investigating officer is adamant that a medical examination be carried out despite the child's or teen's refusal to do so. The law remains quiet regarding the next steps to take in this kind of case. If the victim is a minor, the matter can only be heard by India's Special Courts. When a child's age is unknown, the law does not yet establish a mechanism to find out how old they are.

The crime causes serious physical harm to children. The child's mental health may be jeopardised. In some cases, such as when a private hospital is required for treatment, the parents may simply not be able to pay it. Payment for such procedures is not guaranteed by any legal provisions. The child's safety or even their social isolation could be jeopardised due to social obstacles. The child's family may have to uproot their lives and seek out new opportunities for the child's education and work if this happens.

A number of children's rights have not been fulfilled. The unique concerns and opinions of the youngster have gone unheard by the courts. Victims, especially children, have a right to be informed. This right ensures that details on the case will be disclosed. A right to protection must be assured to the victims. As a result, the victim will always be protected from the perpetrator. The right to be physically present is another fundamental right.

Typically, the matter of victim compensation and rehabilitation plans is considered by the judge. The child victims have not received interim or ultimate compensation in 99% of the instances, according to the Supreme Court of India. According to the Compensation programs for victims, a victim of a sexual assault may be eligible to receive up to 700,000 as restitution from the court. This amount is insufficient, particularly in circumstances where the child suffered a severe damage, as the Delhi High Court recognised in *X Vs. State of Nct of Delhi &Anr*⁷. It is possible that the amount prescribed will not be enough to pay for medical treatment. The Delhi Legal Services Authority was ordered by the court to compensate the child 10,500,000 (700,000 + 50% of 700,000). The child was rightfully served in this exceptional circumstance. Individuals who have been victims of human trafficking should have the freedom to chart their own course towards higher education and the development of employable skills. In order to properly care for young victims, each district hospital should establish a specialised unit. According to the court's ruling in *HanumanthaMogaveera v. State of Karnataka*⁸, children should be sent to private hospitals if they need medical attention. To help children recover from trauma, states should make mental health specialists accessible to everybody. The state should pay for the rehabilitation.

Challenges Faced by Specialized Courts

The objectives of special courts have been impeded by their chaotic and unorganised establishment, as well as by the preference to "designate" instead than build supplemental infrastructure. Information regarding their performance is scarce. Nevertheless, existing figures suggest that it has fluctuated between deplorable and insufficient. At the

⁶Ferrao, R. (2024) 'Special Courts for Children; Lessons learnt from India', *International Journal for Court Administration*, 15(2). doi:10.36745/ijca.485.

⁷X Vs. State of Nct of Delhi &Anr, CRL.A. 63/2022 decided on 20.10.2022

⁸HanumanthaMogaveera v. State of Karnataka, ILR 2021 KAR 3469.

commencement of 2022, the backlog in fast-track courts exceeded 1 million cases, with 2,26,000 unresolved POCSO cases⁹.

The majority of cases adjudicated by POCSO courts in 2019 took anywhere from one to ten years, although the POCSO Act states that special court should be finished within a time period of 1 year¹⁰. A staggering number of rape cases (89.5%) and POCSO cases (88.8%) in fast-track courts have not yet been addressed as of December 2019. In 2018, the NCRB reported that cases in these courts were dragged more longer than one year in 78% of times, three years in 42%, and five years in 17%¹¹.

Their failure is caused by a multitude of factors. The reality is that special courts face the same or even more severe problems than regular courts since they are mostly defined rather than created¹². Without more resources or support staff, judges already overwhelmed with caseloads are forced to take on additional types of cases. Every instance's resolution rate would fall. Faster case resolution also won't happen unless specialised courts are more efficient or procedural mandates are relaxed.

The arbitrary construction of special courts by decisions made by the judiciary and the executive branch leads to the prioritisation of particular types of offences above others in order to facilitate the speedy resolution of certain offences. Despite the fact that decisions are delivered in regard to current cases, there is still no basis for the establishment of special courts through legislation. There are many instances in which it is prompted by an instinctive reaction to certain occurrences, such as the financial frauds that occurred in the 1990s.

It appears that the lack of proper infrastructure and funding for specialized courts is indicative of a more systemic issue with the way courts are established in the country¹³. It would appear that special courts, which were established without extensive assessment of their efficacy, offer a tempting remedy to the intricate issues encountered by the judicial system. In reality, special and fast-track courts often behave differently than their designations. Inadequate infrastructure, overworked judges, and inadequate funding are all issues that they exacerbate and reflect. Special courts can only remain in theory unless they are really set up, complete with their own unique infrastructure and effective processes.

Conclusion

The research highlights the importance of Special Courts established by the POCSO Act in safeguarding sexually assaulted children in India. Although these courts have made a lot of progress in delivering child-sensitive justice, problems such as overburdened judges, lack of infrastructure, and delays continue to plague the system. There is a compromise on the child-

⁹Thakur, P. (2022) *Fast-track courts going slow, pendency crosses 10L cases: India News - Times of India, The Times of India*. Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/fast-track-courts-going-slow-pendency-crosses-10l-cases/articleshow/89581001.cms> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

¹⁰Salve, P. (2021) *What's slowing down India's fast-track courts, Indiaspend*. Available at: <https://www.indiaspend.com/police-judicial-reforms/whats-slowing-down-indias-fast-track-courts-700397> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

¹¹Aggarwal, Y. (2020) *Why have fast track courts failed in India?, The Leaflet*. Available at: <https://theleaflet.in/why-have-fast-track-courts-failed-in-india/> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

¹²Bajpai, G.S. and Smriti, K.P. (2019) *Slow fast-track courts, Deccan Herald*. Available at: <https://www.deccanherald.com/opinion/main-article/slow-fast-track-courts-730501.html> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

¹³Prakash, S. and Khaitan, N. (2017) *Fast-track courts: Flattering to deceive, DNA India*. Available at: <https://www.dnaindia.com/analysis/column-fast-track-courts-flattering-to-deceive-2372689> (Accessed: 18 December 2024).

friendly environment, which is required to reduce trauma. Whereas protection under the POCSO Act is provided in regards to in-camera proceedings with trained professionals, there seems to be a lacuna in the medical and psychological support systems and compensation available to victims.

In conclusion, though Special Courts are indeed important, reforms must be effected to ensure that there would be dedicated infrastructure, smoother procedures, and better victim rehabilitation to deliver timely and effective justice for children.